

esiwace

CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE IN SIMULATION OF WEATHER
AND CLIMATE IN EUROPE

At a glance

Title:

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe

Instrument:

European research infrastructures (including e-Infrastructures), Work programme 2014-2015, Call EINFRA-5-2015, Topic H2020-EINFRA-2015-1 (RIA), H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. - Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures

EC Contribution: 4.95 million euro

Duration: 48 months

Start Date: 1 September 2015

Consortium:

16 partners from 7 countries

Project Coordinator:

German Climate Computing Center - Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH (Germany)

<http://www.esiwace.eu>

Project Objectives

ESiWACE substantially improves efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms by supporting the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling in High Performance Computing environments

Project Impacts

Weather and climate computing have always been amongst the key drivers for High Performance Computing development, with domain specific scientific and technical requirements that stretch the capability and capacity of existing software and hardware to the limits

By developing solutions for Europe and at European scale, ESiWACE directly impacts on the competitiveness of the European High Performance Computing industry by opening the potential for engendering new products, providing opportunities for exploitation beyond the project itself and enhancing the skills base of staff in both industry and academia

Project Features

ESiWACE is thematic: it focuses on the High Performance Computing application domain of climate and weather modeling

ESiWACE is transversal: it covers several aspects of computational science

ESiWACE is challenge-driven: climate and weather predictability represents a major societal issue

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The Methodology

ESiWACE targets the convergent use of Earth System Modelling for weather and climate science (ESM). Global Earth System Models, the post-processing methods to handle the vast amounts of data they produce, and their complex end-to-end workflow, are the central tools for weather and climate science - in both research and operations

ESiWACE leverages two established European networks, namely, the European Network for Earth System modelling (ENES) <https://verc.enes.org> representing the European climate modelling community and the world leading European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) <http://www.ecmwf.int>

ESiWACE addresses three major themes:

- The “Scalability” theme will coordinate performance assessment and upgrade development of state-of-the-art community models and tools, for example, ESMs, coupling and I/O technologies
- The “Usability” theme will focus on the ease-of-use of available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures for ESM
- The “Exploitability” theme addresses major data handling barriers that hinder exploiting HPC for ESM

Governance and Engagement

We aim at creating a governance structure, which ensures that the users from the weather and climate community inside and outside the ESiWACE consortium contribute to the definition of the scope and priorities of the services to be provided

Interested in getting to know more?

Contact the ESiWACE Project Office

E-Mail: esiwace@dkrz.de

Web: www.esiwace.eu

Or follow us on Twitter: @esiwace

Project Partners

Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH
(Coordinator; DE)

European Centre for Medium-Range
Weather Forecasts
(Co-coordinator; UK)

Centre National de la Recherche
Scientifique IPSL (FR)

Max-Planck-Institut für Meteorologie (DE)

Centre Européen de Recherche et de
Formation Avancée en Calcul Scientifique
(FR)

Barcelona Supercomputing Center (ES)

Science and Technology Facilities Council
(UK)

Met Office (UK)

The University of Reading (UK)

Sveriges meteorologiska och hydrologiska
institut (SE)

National University of Ireland Galway -
Irish Centre for High End Computing (IE)

Centro Euro-mediterraneo sui cambiamenti
climatici (IT)

Deutscher Wetterdienst (DE)

Seagate Systems UK Limited (UK)

BULL SAS (FR)

Allinea Software Limited (UK)

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